

**NEW METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION
OF LEDIPASVIR AND SOFOSBUVIR IN BULK AND ITS DOSAGE FORM BY REVERSE PHASE
HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY**

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ABSTRACT:

AIM: The purpose of the present study is to develop a simple, precise, accurate, reproducible, sensitive and economical method for the determination of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir by RP-HPLC method,

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir pure drugs (API), Combination Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir tablets (**Harvoni**), Distilledwater, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Methanol, Potassium di hydrogen orthophosphate buffer, Ortho-phosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are purchased from Rankem. WATERS HPLC2695SYSTEM

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The chromatographic separation was achieved with Kromasil C-18(4.6 x 150mm, 5 μ m). The optimized method utilized a mobile phase of 55% 0.01N KH₂PO₄ and 45% Acetonitrile, with a flow rate of 1ml/min and UV Detector at 220 nm with good resolution and satisfactory plate count. Retention times were 2.402 min for Ledipasvir and 3.526 min for Sofosbuvir. The method developed was validated according to ICH guidelines where all validation parameters were within the acceptable range. linearity was observed from 0–60 μ g/ml for sofosbuvir and 0-13.5 μ g/ml for ledipasvir. The correlation coefficient was 0.995 for ledipasvir and sofosbuvir. The mean percentage recovery for the developed method was found to be 100.28 % for Ledipasvir and 100.25 % for Sofosbuvir. The method developed was found to be robust. So the method developed was suitable for the quantitative analysis of Ledipasvir and sofosbuvir in Bulk and Fixed dosage form as the method developed is accurate, precise, linear, reproducible, robust and sensitive.

Keywords: Ledipasvir, Sofosbuvir, RP-HPLC, orthophosphoric acid, Acetonitrile, Methanol

Ledipasvir, previously known as GS5885, is an inhibitor of the Hepatitis-C Virus (HCV) NS5A protein required for viral RNA replication and assembly of HCV virions. Although its exact mechanism of action is unknown, it is postulated to prevent hyperphosphorylation of NS5A which is required for viral production^[3].

Sofosbuvir is a pro drug nucleotide analog used as part of combination therapy to treat hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection or to treat co-infection of HIV and HCV. After metabolism to the active antiviral agent 2'-deoxy-2'-α-fluoro-β-C-methyluridine-5'-triphosphate (also known as GS-461203), the triphosphate serves as a defective substrate for the NS5B protein, an RNA-dependent RNA polymerase required for replication of viral RNA. Sofosbuvir along with other nucleotide inhibitors of the HCV RNA polymerase aids in decrease in development of viral resistance. This is an important advantage of sofosbuvir in comparison with other HCV drugs that target other viral enzymes like protease, for which rapid resistance development is an important cause of therapeutic failure. More recently, sofosbuvir has become available as a fixed dose drug combination product with ledipasvir (trade name Harvoni) used for the treatment of chronic Hepatitis C, an infectious liver disease caused by infection with Hepatitis C Virus (HCV). Approved in October 2014 by the FDA, ledipasvir and sofosbuvir are direct acting antiviral agents indicated for the treatment of HCV genotype 1 with or without cirrhosis^{[4][5],[6],[7]}.

Fig no 1: structure of ledipasvir^[1]

Fig no 2: structure of sofosbuvir^[2]

The prime focus of this study is to develop a rapid and reliable RP- High Performance liquid Chromatography method for the estimation of Ledipasvir and sofosbuvir

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and reagents:

Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir pure drugs (API), Combination Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir tablets (**Harvoni**), Distilled water, Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer, Methanol, Potassium di hydrogen orthophosphate buffer, Orthophosphoric acid. All the above chemicals and solvents are purchased from Rankem.

Instrument's Used:

- WATERS HPLC2695SYSTEM equipped with quaternary pumps, Photo Diode Array detector and Auto sampler integrated with Empower 2 Software. UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T60 with special bandwidth of 2mm and 10mm and matched quartz cells integrated with UV win 6 Software was used for measuring absorbances of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir solutions. pH meter, Ultrasonicator are from BVK enterprises India were used in the study.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weighed 4.5mg of Ledipasvir, 20mg of Sofosbuvir and transferred to 50ml volumetric flasks and 3/4th of diluents was added to these flasks and sonicated for 10 minutes. Flasks were made up with diluents and labeled as Standard stock solution (90µg/ml of Ledipasvir and 400µg/ml Sofosbuvir).

Preparation of Standard working solutions (100% solution): 1ml from each stock solution was pipette out and taken into a 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent.(9µg/ml of Ledipasvir and 4.0µg/ml of Sofosbuvir) .

Preparation of test solution from pharmaceutical formulation: 5 tablets were weighed and the average weight of each tablet was calculated, then the weight equivalent to 1 tablet was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, 50ml of diluents was added and sonicated for 25min, further the volume was made up with diluents and filtered by HPLC filters (900µg/ml of Ledipasvir and 4000µg/ml of Sofosbuvir)

Preparation of Sample working solutions (100% solution): 0.11ml of filtered sample stock solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up with diluent. (9 µg/ml of Ledipasvir and 40 µg/ml of Sofosbuvir).

Preparation of buffer:

0.1% OPA Buffer: 1 ml of ortho phosphoric acid was diluted to 1000 ml with HPLC grade water.

0.01N KH₂PO₄ Buffer: Accurately weighed 1.36gm of Potassium dihydrogen Orthophosphate in a 1000 ml of Volumetric flask add about 900ml of milli-Q water added and degas to sonicate and finally make up the volume with water then pH adjusted to 5.4 with dil. Orthophosphoric acid solution.

Optimized Chromatographic conditions: The mobile phase selected was a mixture of phosphate buffer (pH 5.4) and acetonitrile in the proportion of 55:45% v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min as it resolves the height with retention times of 2.402 min and 3.526 min for Ledipasvir and sofosbuvir respectively. Standard drug solutions were scanned over a range from 200 to 400 nm, and detection was carried out at 220 nm as both the drugs showed reasonably good response with characteristic UV spectrum.

Validation:

The proposed method was validated for specificity, accuracy, and precision, the limit of detection, the limit of quantitation as well as the robustness of the method as per ICH guidelines. Replicate injections of the standard and sample were used to carry out all the studies.

System suitability parameters:

The system suitability parameters were determined by preparing standard solutions of Ledipasvir (9 µg/ml) and Sofosbuvir (40 µg/ml) and the solutions were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Method development: Method development was done by changing various mobile phase ratios and various column types like Discovery C18 and Kromosil C18 to get appropriate peaks.

fig no 3: Optimised chromatogram of Ledipasvir and sofosbuvir

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines

Table no 1: System suitability parameters

S. no	Ledipasvir			Sofosbuvir			USP Resolution
Inj	RT(min)	USP Plate Count	Tailing	RT(min)	USP Plate Count	tailing	
1	2.402	3332	1.08	3.525	3.525	1.05	5.7
2	2.403	3161	1.05	3.526	3.526	1.05	5.9
3	2.404	3185	1.08	3.526	3.526	1.06	5.8
4	2.404	3220	1.07	3.529	3.529	1.05	5.7

fig no 4: system stability chromatogram

According to ICH guidelines plate count should be more than 2000, tailing factor should be less than 2 and resolution must be more than 2. All the system suitable parameters were passed and were within the limits.

fig no 5: chromatogram of blank

fig no 6: chromatogram of placebo

fig no 7: chromatogram of ledipasvir and sofosbuvir
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Retention times of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir were 2.402 min and 3.526 min respectively No interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs were found in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Linearity:

Linearity was determined between the concentration ranges of 0-60 µg/ml for Sofosbuvir and 0-13.5 µg/ml for Ledipasvir. The injection was done twice for each concentration of Sofosbuvir and Ledipasvir. The correlation coefficient value was found to be 0.999 for Sofosbuvir and Ledipasvir. Linearity Results were shown in **Table** , and Calibration graphs were shown in **Fig. 8** and **9**.

Table no 2: Linearity values for Ledipasvir and sofosbuvir

Ledipasvir		Sofosbuvir	
Conc(µg/ml)	Peak area	Conc(µg/ml)	Peak area
0	0	0	0
2.25	92597	10	654389
4.5	167714	20	1146923
6.75	244720	30	1719648
9	323447	40	2289104
11.25	404070	50	2868980
13.5	484887	60	3446759

fig no 8: Linearity of ledipasvir

fig no 9: linearity of sofosbuvir

Accuracy^[8]:

The accuracy of an approach is the measurement of intimacy with respect to actuality worth for the sample and was determined by preparing concentration levels of 50%, 100%, 150% and was injected thrice into the chromatographic system, and percentage recovery was calculated. The results are tabulated in **Table 3** and **Table 4**

Table no 3 Accuracy values of Ledipasvir

Ledipasvir				
Recovery level	% Recovery			% Recovery average
	Set-I	Set-II	Set-III	
50%	100.68	100.39	99.68	100.28
100%	100.49	100.01	101.15	
150%	99.77	100.68	99.66	

Table no 4: Accuracy values of Sofosbuvir

Sofosbuvir				
Recovery level	% Recovery			% Recovery average
	Set-I	Set-II	Set-III	
50%	99.76	100.74	100.04	100.25
100%	100.64	100.98	99.65	
150%	99.93	100.11	100.38	

Precision^[9]:

The % RSD for Inter-Day precision was found to be 0.7% while the % RSD for Intra-day precision was found to be 1.0 %. The results indicates the method is precise.

Robustness^[10]:

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.9ml/min), Flow plus (1.1ml/min), mobile phase minus (50B:50A), mobile phase plus (60B:40A), temperature minus (25°C) and temperature plus (35°C) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

Table no 5: Robustness of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir

S.no	Condition	%RSD of Ledipasvir	%RSD of Sofosbuvir
1	Flowrate(-) 0.9ml/min	0.4	1.1
2	Flowrate(+) 1.1ml/min	0.8	0.3
3	Mobilephase(-)50:50A	1.6	0.2
4	Mobilephase(+)60B:40A	0.5	0.7
5	Temperature(-)25°C	0.5	0.2
6	Temperature(+)35°C	0.9	1.3

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ)

The limit of detection and limit of quantification for Lepidasvir and sofosbuvir was found to be 0.05 and 0.16 , 0.41 and 1.23 respectively.

CONCLUSION:

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir in Tablet dosage form. Retention time of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir were found to be 2. 402 min and 3.526 % RSD of the Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir were and found to be 0.4and 0.7 respectively. %Recovery was obtained as 100.28% and 100.25% for Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir respectively. LOD, LOQ values obtained from regression equations of Ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir were 0.05, 0.16 and 0.41,1.23 respectively. Regression equation of Ledipasvir is $y=35450x+6061$. $y=56827x+27439$ of Sofosbuvir. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors of this paper declares no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. National Center for Biotechnology Information (2025). PubChem Compound Summary for CID 67505836, Ledipasvir. Retrieved May 29, 2025 from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Ledipasvir>.
2. National Center for Biotechnology Information (2025). PubChem Compound Summary for CID 45375808, Sofosbuvir. Retrieved May 29, 2025 from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Sofosbuvir>.
3. Kwon, H. J., Xing, W., Chan, K., Niedziela-Majka, A., Brendza, K. M., Kirschberg, T., Kato, D., Link, J. O., Cheng, G., Liu, X., & Sakowicz, R. Direct binding of ledipasvir to HCV NS5A: mechanism of resistance to an HCV antiviral agent. *PloS one*, (2015). 10(4), e0122844. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0122844>
4. Yancey, A., Armbruster, A., & Tackett, S.. Sofosbuvir, a New Nucleotide Analogue, for the Treatment of Chronic Hepatitis C Infection. *The Journal of pharmacy technology : jPT : official publication of the Association of Pharmacy Technicians*, (2015) 31(1), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/8755122514548897>.
5. Akshay P. Rote, et.al, DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF LEDIPASVIR AND SOFOSBUVIR IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research*, (2017). 9(6), 291-298. <https://doi.org/10.25004/IJPSDR.2017.090602>
6. Leah A. Burke, Kristen M. Marks,155 - Drugs to Treat Viral Hepatitis,Editor(s): Jonathan Cohen, William G. Powderly, Steven M. Opal,Infectious Diseases (Fourth Edition),Elsevier,2017,Pages 1327-1332.e1,ISBN 9780702062858,<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-7020-6285-8.00155-6>.
7. Ghany, M. G., Nelson, D. R., Strader, D. B., Thomas, D. L., Seeff, L. B., & American Association for Study of Liver Diseases .An update on treatment of genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C virus infection: 2011 practice guideline by the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases. *Hepatology (Baltimore, Md.)*, (2011). 54(4), 1433–1444. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.24641>
8. Lavanya, G., Sunil, M. M. E. M., Eswarudu, M. M., Eswaraiah, M. C., Harisudha, K., & Spandana, B. N. Analytical method validation: an updated review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, (2013). 4(4), 1280. [http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.4\(4\).1280-86](http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.4(4).1280-86)
9. Francisco Raposo, Carolina Ibelli-Bianco, Performance parameters for analytical method validation: Controversies and discrepancies among numerous guidelines, *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, Volume 129, 2020, 115913, ISSN 0165-9936, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2020.115913>.
10. M. Mulholland, Ruggedness testing in analytical chemistry, *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, Volume 7, Issue 10, 1988, Pages 383-389, ISSN 0165-9936, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936\(88\)85089-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936(88)85089-1).